

Table S1. Band parameters of obtained spectrum by LMS and laboratory. D8, D9, D10, D11, D12, D14, D15, D16, and D17 were the LMS spectrum. CE5C-S1, CE5C-S2, and CE5C-S3 were obtained by CE-5 soil samples (CE5C0800YJFM001-1, CE5C0100YJFM002-1 and CE5C0100YJFM002-2) in the laboratory (Liu et al., 2022). The Band parameters of the returned samples were calculated from our calculations using the 450 nm to 2500 nm spectra of Liu et al. (2022). The values in parentheses are the conclusions for Liu et al. (2022).

	B1cen (μm)	B1asy	B2cen (μm)	Area Ratio
D8	0.97	0.15	1.97	0.44
D9	0.98	0.25	2.00	0.24
D10	0.97	0.36	2.02	0.26
D11	0.97	0.46	2.11	0.23
D12	0.97	0.39	2.15	0.27
D14	1.02	0.15	2.02	0.52
D15	1.03	0.16	2.00	0.46
D16	0.99	0.26	1.99	0.50
D17	0.98	0.30	2.05	0.41
CE5C-S1	1.02(1.02)	0.26	2.17(2.22)	0.52
CE5C-S2	1.02(1.02)	0.26	2.20(2.23)	0.47
CE5C-S3	1.02(1.02)	0.27	2.19(2.23)	0.51

Table S2. Band parameters and location of Aristarchus north ejecta continuum removed spectrum from M3 observation M3G20090418T132620.

	X(m)	Y(m)	B1cen (μm)	B1asy	B2cen (μm)	Area Ratio
AR-1	-1444285.83	742297.67	0.99	-0.06	2.09	0.49
AR-2	-1444749.96	744759.43	0.96	-0.01	2.09	0.38
AR-3	-1445178.95	747231.74	0.99	-0.07	2.01	0.43
AR-4	-1445628.16	749678.40	0.99	-0.07	2.01	0.35
AR-5	-1446130.20	752154.26	0.98	-0.11	2.08	0.39
AR-6	-1446544.86	754617.25	0.98	0.11	2.04	0.48
AR-7	-1447011.50	757125.61	1.00	0.11	2.09	0.45
AR-8	-1447447.62	759558.96	1.00	0.08	2.03	0.36

Table S3. Band parameters and location of Harpalus southwest ejecta continuum removed spectrum from M3 observation M3G20090209T033051.

	X(m)	Y(m)	B1cen (μm)	B1asy	B2cen (μm)	Area Ratio
HA-1	-1336.67	1581365.15	0.93	-0.07	1.93	0.77
HA-2	-1338.41	1579689.62	0.95	0.00	1.63	1.30
HA-3	-1340.62	1577606.69	1.03	-0.02	1.62	1.19
HA-4	-1342.79	1575488.77	0.95	-0.02	1.94	0.93
HA-5	-1345.02	1573373.07	0.97	-0.06	2.00	0.62
HA-6	-1347.18	1571251.95	0.96	-0.02	2.05	0.45
HA-7	-1349.36	1569181.48	0.97	0.08	1.96	0.46
HA-8	-1351.50	1567078.21	0.99	0.02	2.00	0.48
HA-9	-1353.68	1564933.22	1.00	0.17	2.00	0.51
HA-10	-1355.85	1562828.64	0.97	0.13	1.98	0.57
HA-11	-1358.01	1560701.49	0.93	0.08	1.95	0.75
HA-12	-1360.13	1558604.60	1.03	-0.10	1.94	0.67
HA-13	-1362.31	1556518.14	1.02	0.15	1.91	1.56

References

Liu, D., Wang, X., Liu, J., Liu, B., Ren, X., Chen, Y., et al. (2022). Spectral interpretation of late-stage mare basalt mineralogy unveiled by Chang'E-5 samples. *Nature Communications*, 13(1).